

Co-creation of radical social innovation in Living Labs: assessing cognitive, relational and contextual conditions

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Abstract

Research on Living Labs highlights their potential to tackle Grand Societal Challenges through social innovation. Yet, further evidence is needed on the conditions and pathways enabling this process. This paper presents research in progress analysing the knowledge conditions under which co-creation initiatives in Living Labs result in social innovations. Theoretically, we explore some of the epistemic aspects of co-creation literature highlighting how radical social innovations result from combinations of knowledge conditions related to cognitive, relational and contextual dimensions (section 2). Empirically, we study focal innovations in 15 European Living Labs in the Agri-food and Healthcare sectors and perform a Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) building on data from semi-structured interviews (section 3). Preliminary findings show that the co-creation of radical social innovations may result from three possible combinations of knowledge conditions at play: in two of these there is direct knowledge integration in response to structured problems, in either centralised networks or well-established organisational settings. A third pathway showcases indirect knowledge integration addressing wicked problems in decentralised collaborations (section 4). These research will provide lessons for both practice and research on co-creation in Living Labs (section 5)

Key words

Living Labs, Social innovation, Knowledge conditions, Co-creation

1. Research rationale

Knowledge and innovation are key for the development of new solutions to Grand Societal Challenges (Köhler, et al., 2019). Living Labs contribute to this by acting as experimentation platforms and open innovation networks, enabling knowledge circulation in the co-creation innovative solutions in real-life settings that accelerate sustainable transitions (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015; Schuurman, et al, 2016; von Wirth, et al, 2019).

While Living Lab scholarship sheds light on their potential to tackle these Grand Challenges (ENoLL, 2025), further evidence is needed on the pathways and conditions enabling experimentation in Living Labs in the context of sustainability transitions (Köhler, et al., 2019). Following Hossain, et al. (2019), the success of Living Labs in delivering innovations depends on mutual learning and knowledge circulation among different actors involved.

Building on this premise, the goal of this research is to identify the knowledge conditions enabling Living Labs to co-create social innovations, focusing on radical innovations embodying new ideas to accelerate solutions for sustainability challenges. The following pages present the theoretical (section 2) and methodological aspects (section 3), as well as a brief summary of early results (section 4) of the cross-case comparison. To conclude, we outline a few implications for research and practice (section 5).

2. Theoretical background: Cognitive, relational and contextual aspects of co-creation

Social innovations are a common outcome of co-creation processes (Ansell & Torfing, 2021; Broekema, Bulder, & Horlings, 2023). These are new or significantly improved products, services or processes “defined by their (social) objectives to improve the welfare of individuals or communities” (OECD, 2018, p. 252). In the context of sustainability transitions, radical social innovations are needed to accelerate the process of tackling Grand Societal Challenges (Geels, 2002; Köhler, et al., 2019), and Living Labs play a key role in producing both incremental and radical innovations (Leminen, Nyström, Westerlund, & Kortelainen, 2016; Hossain, Leminen, & Westerlund, 2019), the former building on already available knowledge, while the latter is based on entirely new ideas and knowledge sources (OECD, 2018).

Living Labs operate as open innovation networks where new and existing knowledge sources are accessed and circulated (Schuurman, 2015; Leminen, Westerlund, & Nyström, 2012). This is often done through co-creation aiming at tackling wicked societal

problems and creating public value (Haug & Mergel, 2021; Ansell & Torfing, 2021a). While the role of knowledge in co-creation has been not been fully explored, we follow Centeno’s (2025) conceptualisation, shedding light on its cognitive, relational and contextual dimensions. This conceptual approach is summarised in figure 1 and further explained in the remainder of the section.

Figure 1. Knowledge conditions of co-creation: cognitive, relational and contextual aspects shaping the co-creation of radical social innovations

Source: own elaboration based on Centeno (2025).

In this approach, knowledge refers not just to information, but to “an understanding of information and the ability to use information for different purposes” (OECD, 2018, p. 46). In this sense, knowledge has a content-related dimension, as well as a relational one highlighting the interactions between the different actors involved in building understandings of public problems (Bouwen, 2001; Brugnach & Ingram, 2012). This underlines the cognitive and relational aspects of knowledge.

Cognitive conditions refer to “how actors in co-creation, whether individuals or organisations, valorise, combine, and expect to learn from different knowledge sources” (Centeno, 2025, p. 22). This often features as the integration of diverse of knowledge

sources including technical and scientific approaches, but also knowledge from experts-by-experience from citizens (Ansell & Torfing, 2021; Jaspers & Tuurnas, 2023; van Dijck & Steen, 2023).

In turn, relational conditions represent knowledge circulation patterns in the form of network structures of collaboration allowing actors to access new ideas (Bovaird, 2007; Meijer, 2011). In this regard, Living Lab research suggests that distributed network structures are more effective in delivering radical social innovations, compared to centralised networks, since the former enable the access to new ideas (Leminen, Nyström, Westerlund, & Kortelainen, 2016).

Finally, contextual conditions refer to the situated nature of knowledge, responding to the local features of the settings there it is produced and circulated (van Buuren, 2009; Feldman, Khademian, Ingram, & Schneider, 2006). These may respond to well-established organisational settings and features (Voorberg, Bekkers, Timeus, Tonurist, & Tummers, 2017), as well as to the local complex (wicked) problems under concern in co-creation processes (Noordegraaf, Douglas, Geuijen, & Van Der Steen, 2019). Co-creation in Living Labs may lead to radical social innovations as a response to wicked problems, and their success depends on an enabling and distributed organisational setting for collaboration.

3. Methodological approach

We perform a Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) allowing us to explain the occurrence of radical social innovation (outcome) as resulting from the conditions described above and different combinations of these, assessing if these are necessary or sufficient conditions (Schneider & Wagemann, 2010). The outcome and conditions are regarded as sets, and the cases as having a membership (or not) to these combinations (Ragin, 2008), depending on the presence or absence of the outcome and conditions in each case. Presence or absence is measured by scoring the cases from 0.00 to 1.00, where 1.00 represents full presence and 0.00 describes the opposite. The result is the identification of combinations of conditions or configurational pathways with cases having a membership to one or the other. Due to the word-limit of this paper, we do not elaborate on the specifics of this method, but we recommend readers unfamiliar with QCA to consult Mello (2021) for further detail.

Our sample comprises 15 European Living Lab organisations with a current membership to the ENoLL, located in a selection of countries (BE, NL, CH, ES, GR) and working in the

Agrifood and Healthcare sectors. Within each Living Lab organisation, we emphasised the focal or single most important innovation, as identified by interviewees (OECD, 2018).

Following the conceptualisation presented in the previous section, figure 1 and Appendix 2 summarise our QCA framework comprising the outcome and causal conditions, as well as the sub-conditions operationalising them. Here, the absence/presence of the outcome depends on the identification of incremental or radical innovations, respectively. This approach suggests that Living Labs co-create radical social innovations (RSI) when there is Direct Knowledge Integration (DKI) in Distributed Collaboration Networks (DCN), as well as Established Organisational Settings (EOS) and when the initiatives respond to Wicked Problem (WP).

These conditions are present, in turn, when either of the sub-conditions are present (using Boolean operator OR). The latter were substantiated with qualitative evidence from semi-structured interviews with 28 Living Lab practitioners. Documentary review was conducted for data triangulation, including web pages, diffusion documents, academic papers, among others.

Data calibration follows QCA best practice to transform qualitative evidence to quantitative scores from 0.00 to 1.00, representing the absence and presence of the outcome and causal conditions is measured, respectively (Basurto & Speer, 2012). For word limit reasons we have not included details on the raw and calibrated data for the cases, but an overview is provided in appendix 1. Additional detail on the QCA framework, indicators and calibration thresholds is provided in Appendix 2. Further information on this matter is available upon request.

4. Early findings: Pathways to social innovation in Living Labs

After running the analysis in the fsQCA software (version 4.1) (Ragin, 2017), preliminary results¹¹ for the analysis of necessity show that none of the conditions, neither their presence nor absence, was necessary for the occurrence of the outcome (RSI). This is also the case in the absence of the outcome (~RSI). These results mean that the single influence of these knowledge conditions is not enough for co-creation to lead to either radical or incremental social innovations, but their combined effect is required. Naturally, we expect broader factors to influence these processes.

¹¹ Since this is research-in-progress, detailed QCA results regarding consistency and coverage indicators are omitted in this version but are to be presented during the Open Living Lab Days. Same applies for the analysis of sufficiency and its resulting truth table and intermediate solution.

In turn, the analysis of sufficiency reveals three possible combinations of conditions leading to radical social innovations. These are alternative co-creation pathways to radical social innovation, where knowledge plays distinctive roles, shaping different configurations.

The first pathway represents co-creation processes with direct knowledge integration (DKI) in centralised network interactions (~DCN) where the challenge being addressed is a structured problem (~WP) for which there is either a high level of certainty or agreement. Here we find two illustrative cases based in agri-food research organisations with a strong tradition of developing participatory research initiatives involving different stakeholders and alternative mechanisms for knowledge integration. Examples include ILVO's Living Lab Animal Husbandry (LLAH) (BE_A_2) and WaterCampus Leeuwarden hosted by WETSUS (NL_A_1). These cases exhibit differentiated starting points for knowledge hybridisation (i.e. combination of knowledge sources) in the form of varying mechanisms for problem identification, either top-down or bottom-up.

The second pathway also features knowledge integration (DKI) tackling structured problems (~WP), in this case enabled by well-established organisational settings (EOS). In this configuration we find three illustrative cases, including the already mentioned WaterCampus Leeuwarden (NL_A_1), as well as two cases in health: the MINDLab by INTRAS Foundation (ES_H_1) and the Living and Care Lab (LiCaLab) at Thomas More University of Applied Sciences (BE_H_1). Knowledge integration is enabled by employing explicit community management strategies for close interaction with end-users (e.g. LiCaLab), or by developing long-term innovation trajectory (~20 years) championed by individuals conducting research on the issue in question (e.g. WaterCampus and MINDLab). For example, in one of MINDLab's initiatives on dementia, this relies on close collaboration with international partners and end-users:

There's been lots of work around in terms of co-design, but we've developed it in this particular context with (...) people's early-stage dementia. So, what we did pioneer was really including them, not going to the carers but really trying to include them as people who would have their own, you know, opinion and can have, you know... as people. Not as people with dementia, but as people who are valued (Interview_ES_H_1_3, 2025).

Finally, the third pathway identified showcases indirect knowledge integration (~DKI) through collaborations in distributed networks (DCN) that enable to address wicked societal challenges (WP). Examples include ILVO's Living Lab Agrifood Technology (BE_A_1), where the highly technical character of innovations entail indirect forms of

knowledge integration. Here, end-user expertise complements scientific knowledge to enhance the sustainability of agri-food systems. Another example is Alimentta (ES_A_2), which facilitates knowledge integration by mediating between key organisations in the sector and forming working groups to sustain collaborations that promote sustainable transitions in agrifood systems.

5. Implications for research and practice

This research-in-progress intends to better grasp the role of knowledge in co-creation processes taking place in Living Labs that develop social innovations in Agrifood and Healthcare. By addressing the case of Living Labs, it adds to co-creation scholarship by clarifying the conditions explaining the development of innovative outcomes (Rodriguez-Müller, Casiano-Flores, Albrecht, Steen, & Crompvoets, 2021). It also contributes to a better understanding of the role of knowledge as an impact pathway for the co-creation of social innovations (Ansell & Torfing, 2021).

In practical terms, our empirical findings highlight some of the key aspects to consider for co-creation processes to be successful in Living Labs that aim at radical social innovation. The identified co-creation pathways may be useful for Living Lab practitioners as guiding roadmaps for the strategic management of innovation journeys. Next steps include completion of the qualitative data analysis, which will provide further lessons learned based on interviews with Living Lab practitioners across Europe. As such, this research will deliver systematic comparative evidence to identify best practices and lessons learned from Living Labs facilitating co-creation processes.

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Appendix 1 Basic information on Living Lab organisations and their focal innovations

Case code	Living Lab name	Living Lab host organisation	Focal innovation identified
BE_A_1	Living Lab Agrifood Technology	ILVO – Flanders	Smart weed detection system using drone and imaging technology
BE_A_2	Living Lab Animal Husbandry	ILVO – Flanders	Alternative automatised methods for cattle feeding/milking
BE_A_3	Living Lab Circulair	Inagro VZW	Combination of fruit vegetable cultivation and insect farming to maximise greenhouse use
BE_H_1	Living and Care Lab - LiCaLab	Thomas More University	Device and methods to support breathing and tackle sleeping disorders
BE_H_2	imec.living labs	IMEC	Smart speaker and sensor to facilitate care service provision for senior people
CH_H_1	Senior-Lab	HEdS La Source; HEIG-VD; ECAL (HES-SO)	Alarm system in care service provision for senior people, using electricity consumption data
CH_H_2	Living Lab for Special Needs	HES-SO Valais-Wallis	Prototype of electric wheelchair enhancing mobility access through mechanical arms
ES_A_1	Food&HealthLab	University of Valencia	Human milk bank and mobile medical unit for collecting breast milk donations in Peru
ES_A_2	Alimentta a	Alimentta, Think Tank	Insertion of traditional wheat varieties in Agro-ecological Local Food Systems
ES_H_1	MINDLa b	INTRAS Foundation	Design solutions that support people with dementia with self-empowerment and social engagement

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ES_H_2	NeuroLab	ADACEN Navarra	Adapted exoskeleton enhancing therapy for people recovering from neuronal damage
GR_A_1	InoFA	Internet of Food Alliance Support Office IKE	Circular Bioeconomy Business Models in waste streams of agro sectors: grape, olive and stone fruit
GR_H_1	Thess-AHALL	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Elderly home care coach assistant via projected and tangible interface
NL_A_1	Water Campus Leeuwarden	WETSUS	Method for production of bioplastic from wastewater
NL_H_1	Care Innovation Center	Stichting Care Innovation Center West-Brabant	Device for enhancing access to rehabilitation of hand damage

Source: own elaboration.

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Appendix 2 Summary of operationalisation for Outcome and Causal conditions

Set membership rules for conditions		Set membership rules for sub-conditions	
Direct Knowledge Integration (DKI)	Fully present if: Bottom-up initial knowledge input OR Learning through direct interaction	Initial Knowledge Input	0.00 = Top-down 1.00 = Bottom-up
	Fully absent if: Top-down initial knowledge input AND Learning through indirect interaction	Learning through interaction	0.00 = Undirect interactions 1.00 = Direct interactions
Distributed Collaboration Networks (DCN)	Fully present if: Relatively high number of project partners OR Living Lab supports external solution	Number of project partners	0.00 = ≤5 partners 0.33 = 6 to 10 partners 0.66 = 11 to 20 partners 1.00 = >20 partners
	Fully absent if: Relatively low number of project partners AND Living Lab supports internal solution	Living Lab role in solution	0.00 = Developed internally 1.00 = Developed externally
Established Organisational Setting (EOS)	Fully present if: LL has a shared governance structure OR LL has high number of years as ENoLL member	LL governance structure	0.00 = Single Org 1.00 = Multiple
	Fully absent if:	Years of experience (since ENoLL membership)	0.00 = ≤ 2 years

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	LL has a centralised governance structure AND LL has low number of years as ENoLL member		0.33 = 3 – 5 years 0.66 = 6 – 10 years 1.00 = > 10 years
Wicked Problem (WP)	Fully present if: There is low certainty regarding the problem OR there is low agreement on the values and desired scenarios	Low level of knowledge certainty on the issue to be addressed	0.00 = High certainty 1.00 = Low certainty
	Fully absent if: There is high certainty regarding the problem AND there is high agreement on the values and desired scenarios	Low level of agreement on values and interests at stake	0.00 = High agreement 1.00 = Low agreement

